

Universitat
de les Illes Balears

MASTER'S THESIS

DETECTING SALINITY FRONTS FROM SATELLITE OBSERVATIONS

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Master's Degree in Advanced Physics and Applied Mathematics
(Specialty on Geophysical Fluids)

Centre for Postgraduate Studies

Academic year 2023-24

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Key words:

mesoscale, Lagrangian simulations,
remote sensing, sea surface salinity.

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Abstract

Small-scale variability is fundamental to ocean circulation, air-sea interactions, and biogeochemical processes. In many locations, salinity variations play a more significant role than temperature in shaping density fronts. Unfortunately, current satellite data on sea surface salinity (SSS) can only capture features down to 40 km. This study focuses on analysing mesoscale variability (≤ 25 km) by reconstructing SSS data from satellite observations in the southwest Atlantic, in particular at the Brazil-Malvinas Confluence (BMC). This region is characterised with strong mesoscale structures and high biological activity due to the interaction of western boundary currents and cross-shelf activity. The numerical advection of satellite SSS fields using altimetric geostrophic currents produces a Lagrangian reconstruction that captures finer-scale details. These reconstructed fields are then validated with *in-situ* salinity measurements obtained via thermosalinograph. Results show that reconstructed SSS fields capture mesoscale structures detected by *in-situ* observations at the region and improves the effective resolution of SSS satellite observations.

Acronyms

- ACC** Antarctic Circumpolar Current. 11
- BC** Brazil Current. 11–14, 23, 25, 29
- BMC** Brazil-Malvinas Confluence. 11–16, 29, 30
- ISAS** In Situ Analysis System. 9, 17, 18, 23, 29
- MC** Malvinas Current. 11–14, 23, 25, 29
- PPW** la Plata river Plume Waters. 14
- PS** Patagonian Shelf. 11, 12, 18
- RdlP** Río de la Plata. 12–14, 25
- RMSD** Root-mean-square Difference. 21, 26, 28
- SA** South Atlantic. 11, 29, 30
- SACW** South Atlantic Central Waters. 13, 14
- SASW** Subantarctic Shelf Waters. 14
- SD** Standard Deviation. 21, 26, 28
- SMAP** Soil Moisture Active Passive. 9, 17, 23–25, 29, 30
- SMOS** Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity. 9, 17, 23–30
- SSH** Sea Surface Height. 15
- SSS** Sea Surface Salinity. 14–18, 20, 23–30
- SST** Sea Surface Temperature. 14
- STSF** Subtropical Shelf Front. 14
- STSW** Subtropical Shelf Waters. 14
- TSG** Thermosalinograph. 15, 18, 20, 21, 23, 25–28
- TW** Tropical Waters. 13

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Introduction

1.1 Description of the region

The Brazil-Malvinas Confluence (BMC), located in the South Atlantic (SA) basin, is a key region of the oceanic circulation system. It is one of the world's most energetic regions (Chelton et al., 2011) characterised by high biological activity. Primary productivity, as measured by surface chlorophyll-a concentration, in the SA portion is on average twice as large as that in the Indian and Pacific basins. The high primary productivity is mostly attributed to the exceptional chlorophyll blooms over the Patagonian Shelf (PS) and the export of shelf waters to the deep ocean (Guinder et al., 2024).

1.1.1 Large scale circulation

The SA Ocean thermocline circulation is primarily dominated by the SA Gyre, a subtropical anticyclonic gyre located between the Intertropical Convergence Zone in the north and the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) to the south. To the east, the gyre is formed by the Benguela Current, an eastern boundary current that flows northward carrying cold upwelled waters from the inshore region of the western African coast. The west-flowing South Equatorial Current forms the northern boundary of the gyre and is linked to a western boundary current known as the Brazil Current (BC; figure 1.1) which flows southward and carries warm water into the BMC region. The mean circulation of the gyre exhibits strong interdecadal oscillations and significant wind-driven circulation (E. Palma and Matano, 2018).

The Malvinas Current (MC) carries subantarctic water from the ACC, rounding east of the Falklands/Malvinas Islands and along the PS (figure 1.1) and meets the BC at approximately 38°S creating a thermohaline front at the BMC zone. At the BMC, the interaction between warm and salty waters from the BC and cold and relatively fresh MC waters generates strong thermohaline fronts. The BC separates from the shelf break at ~36.5°S while the MC retroflects at ~38.8°S, creating a zone in between with high kinetic energy and strong mesoscale structures, where most of the cross-shelf exchanges of the Southwestern Atlantic take place (Guerrero et al., 2014; Manta et al., 2022).

The location of the BMC front varies depending on the mass transport of both western boundary currents. For example, a weakening of the northern branch of the ACC might cause a decrease of the MC transport and a southward drift of the BMC (Combes and Matano, 2014). Additionally, wind stress curl over the subtropical basin sets an annual periodicity on the BC transport which causes changes in the orientation of the front, from N-S in winter to NW-SE in summer (Piola and Matano, 2001).

Figure 1.1: Mean surface circulation schematic in the western South Atlantic. The red colour palette corresponds to the mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE) in cm^2/s^2 derived from altimetry data over the period 1993-2022. Only values above $300 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ are shown. The blue colour palette corresponds to the mean Sea Surface Salinity from *in-situ* data. Only the 32, 33.1, and 33.4 psu isohalines contours are shown.

1.1.2 Shelf circulation

The southwest Atlantic circulation reflects that of the adjacent MC and BC currents, with a northward transport over the PS and a southward transport over the Brazil shelf. Between $\sim 35^\circ\text{S}$ and $\sim 30^\circ\text{S}$, the shelf circulation is characterised by a strong wind-driven seasonal variability (Combes et al., 2021). During winter the shelf circulation flows northward and waters originated at the PS mix with the freshwaters of Rio de la Plata (RdIP) along the shelf. In summer, the flow intensifies and changes southwards.

The meanders of the BC influence the circulation at the northern portion of the shelf, as well as its upwelling and cross-shelf exchanges (Calado et al., 2010; Combes et al., 2021). At higher latitudes there is the RdIP mouth, located approximately at 36°S , near the BMC, and it discharges $\sim 24,000 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ of freshwater into the PS and afterwards into the BMC region offshore (Manta et al., 2022). The alongshelf freshwater plume created by the RdIP waters exhibits a strong north-south seasonal variability: in winter the river plume extends northwards reaching 28°S while in summer it retracts to 32°S (Piola et al., 2000). This seasonal changes are mainly driven by the dynamics of the western boundary currents and local wind forcing (E. D. Palma et al., 2004).

During winter, the plume is advected off the shelf north of 35°S into the BMC region. During summer, southwesterly winds halt the northward spread over the shelf and little RdlP water is advected offshore (Matano et al., 2014). The cross-shelf exchanges dynamics are different along the shelf. In the northern portion, bottom topography plays a key role in modulating the cross-shelf exchanges, creating a two-layer flowing structure with off-shelf flow in the upper 50 m and an on-shelf flow below it (Combes et al., 2021). At the surface small scale eddy activity strongly influences the export of shelf water offshore. In the southern part of the shelf, exchanges are modulated by intrusions of sub-Antarctic waters at the surface and the entrainment of deep-ocean waters into the shelf (Combes and Matano, 2014). Most of the off-shelf transport is concentrated at the BMC (Combes and Matano, 2018). The location of the detrainment region exhibits a strong seasonal variations (Matano et al., 2014; Guerrero et al., 2014), with the off-shelf flow located farther north of the BMC during winter.

1.1.3 Mesoscale circulation

Mesoscale circulation encompasses processes ranging from 10 to hundreds of kilometres, with durations that can span from a few days to several months. Mesoscale structures in the ocean emerge from instabilities of the large-scale circulations, interactions with the bottom topography, sheared motions between currents and due to forcing mechanisms like wind forcing. These processes are characterised for being more energetic than the mean flow they emerge from (by at least one order of magnitude) and exhibit high vorticities forming spirally filamental ring-like structures known as eddies, filaments, or fronts. Mesoscale eddies have distinct properties compared to their surroundings and transport characteristics such as heat and salinity throughout the ocean. They play a significant role in ocean variability and influence biological quantities, such as nutrient supply in coastal areas.

The off-shelf BMC region is characterised with high mesoscale activity (figure 1.1) which constitutes a main driving mechanism in the mixing of shelf with open-ocean waters. Satellite observations and numerical simulations show mesoscale activity from the BC advecting shelf waters offshore (Manta et al., 2022). The instabilities generated by the western boundary currents separation from the shelf-break create mesoscale eddies that establish a strong connection between the shelf and deep ocean through vertical mixing (Piola and Matano, 2001). The eddy activity over the shelf also plays an important role on the local variability of temperature and salinity fields (Combes et al., 2023).

While anticyclonic activity extends over the eastern part of the BC, cyclonic eddies are uniformly distributed over the shelf, shelfbreak and open ocean. These eddies have strong seasonality over the shelf in phase with the seasonal variations of the shelf circulation (Combes et al., 2023). The southward currents flowing during summer advect warm and salty waters over the shelf and when the circulation weakens the cyclonic eddies formed trap these waters within their core while fresher water is advected northward. Larger scale cyclonic eddies are formed at the western boundary of the BC (slope eddies). These eddies transport nutrient-rich, less saline and colder shelf waters than their surroundings and their structure is significantly deformed by the asymmetric velocity profile faster on the BC side (Combes et al., 2023).

1.1.4 Water masses

The complexity of the circulation extends to the water mass stratification structure. In the upper ocean, the opposing flows of the BC and the MC dominate the distribution of water masses through the confluence of subtropical and subantarctic waters. The Tropical Waters (TW) carried by the BC, formed at low latitudes, are characterised by high temperatures ($\theta > 20^\circ\text{C}$) and high salinity ($S > 36$ psu) (Piola and Matano, 2001). Below the TW, a very stable thermocline and halocline form the South Atlantic Central Water (SACW). In contrast, the

upper layer of the MC waters, originating from subantarctic regions, have colder potential ($\theta < 15^\circ\text{C}$) and lower salinity ($S < 34.2$ psu). These MC waters exhibit distinct thermocline properties compared to the SACW: while the BC has a clear baroclinic stratification, the MC displays a highly barotropic stratification (Piola and Matano, 2001).

Over the shelf, the subtropical shelf waters (STSW) meet the subantarctic shelf waters (SASW) between $\sim 32^\circ\text{S}$ (inner-shelf) and $\sim 36^\circ\text{S}$ (shelf-break; Guerrero et al., 2014) to form the Subtropical Shelf Front (STSF; Piola et al., 2000). The STSF is a density-compensated front and constitutes a path for the entrainment of shelf waters offshore (Piola et al., 2008).

In addition, the RdIP discharge forms the Plata plume waters (PPW) characterised by low salinity ($S < 33.5$ psu). These waters mix with SASW and STSW leading to a sharp gradient of SSS (Guerrero et al., 2014), which is influenced by the seasonal variability of the extension of the plume.

1.2 Importance of salinity

Ocean salinity, along with temperature and pressure, is a component of the equation of state of seawater and is fundamental in determining the density and behaviour of oceanic water masses. Processes such as evaporation, precipitation, ice formation and melting, and river runoffs produce changes in salinity that drive the movement of water masses within the ocean. In the open ocean, sea surface salinity (SSS) ranges from 33 to 37 psu, being lower at coastal zones near river's discharges and in polar regions due to ice melting, and with higher values at regions of high evaporation, such as the eastern Mediterranean or the Red Seas. While sea surface temperature (SST) has a zonal distribution with tropical maximum and polar minimum, the zonal distribution of SSS is double-lobed with high values at subtropical zones of each hemisphere and lower values at polar and tropic regions.

Salinity is considered an essential climate variable for the Global Climate Observing System, serving as an indirect measure of changes in the Earth's hydrological cycle over the ocean. Changes in salinity affect ocean circulation and stratification and contribute to sea level changes (Steele et al., 2008). Additionally, SSS variability on inter-basin regions is associated with changes on the Meridional Overturning Circulation regulation (Häkkinen, 2002). Over the last decades, an increase of geographical contrasts in SSS has been observed; midlatitudes evaporation-dominated waters have become more saline and tropical fresh surface waters and polar regions have become fresher, impacting the ocean interior (Rhein et al., 2013).

The sparsity of the observational record is a limitation for the understanding of the role of SSS on ocean dynamics, especially in the Southern Hemisphere where salinity is an important signature on large-scale ocean variability due to the strong salinity signals associated with inter-basin and inter-gyre exchanges and coastal/deep interactions (e.g., Guerrero et al., 2014; Matano et al., 2014). In this work, we focus on the BMC region where the export of shelf waters to the deep ocean creates the largest signal of SSS variability of the South Atlantic (Guerrero et al., 2014).

1.3 Remote sensing observations

Remote sensing has improved the ability to study large-scale ocean processes by providing different space-time resolution and coverage than *in-situ* observations. While *in-situ* data gives information on the water column, the measurements are only puntual on space and time. In contrast, satellite data has a global coverage and measurements are repetitive on time, but the observations are limited to the ocean surface.

The synoptic view of the global ocean provided by salinity remote sensing observations captures large-scale signal events which are difficult for the *in-situ* data to resolve. It has improved our knowledge on tropical instability waves (e.g., Yin et al., 2014), Rosby waves (e.g., Banks et al., 2016), salinity dynamics on the tropical and subtropical regions (e.g., Hasson et al., 2018) or climate variability (e.g., Vinogradova and Ponte, 2017). However the effective resolution of satellite SSS measurements (≥ 50 km) is insufficient to capture mesoscale dynamics and submesoscale variability.

The most common technique for the characterisation of mesoscale structures in the global ocean is satellite altimetry. Geostrophic currents associated with these structures can be derived from the ocean sea surface height (SSH) measured by altimetric satellites. The interpolated fields from measurements of SSH have daily coverage and they are capable of representing up to mesoscale features. Even, their temporal integration can resolve finer scales (e.g., Lehahn et al., 2018).

1.4 State of the art of Sea Surface Salinity reconstruction

Horizontal advection is a key factor on the evolution of salinity over time across different spatio-temporal scales (Foltz et al., 2004; Grodsky et al., 2017). In particular, mesoscale processes are shown to play a crucial role in SSS small-scale variability (e.g., Pietri et al., 2013). Various simulation methods of passive advection of large-scale salinity through Lagrangian models using currents derived from altimetry have been able to reconstruct salinity fronts at regions with moderate to high eddy kinetic energy (Rogé et al., 2015).

The first passive advection reconstruction was developed by Desprès et al. (2011) in the Irminger Sea, where they used large-scale salinity from a monthly climatology and altimetric currents with $1/3^\circ$ of resolution to reconstruct ~ 10 km scale frontal structures with realistic results when compared with *in-situ* data. Later on, several similar methods using weekly SSS observation-based fields and currents derived from altimetry with $1/4^\circ$ resolution were tested in the Southern Ocean of Tasmania (Dencausse et al., 2014) and some regions of the western Pacific (Rogé et al., 2015), showing good agreement with *in-situ* observations. These Lagrangian reconstruction methods capture smaller-scale salinity variability (≤ 25 km) than SSS remote sensing observations (≥ 40 km) contributing to a better understanding of ocean circulation, air-sea interaction, and biogeochemistry.

Recently, Barceló-Llull et al. (2021) applied a Lagrangian reconstruction technique to the north-west Atlantic Ocean aiming to downscale satellite SSS observations. This region is highly influenced by the Gulf Stream and is characterised by large-scale salinity gradients and horizontal stirring. Both SSS satellite observations and altimetric currents used in the method have a spatial grid resolution of $1/4^\circ$ and the reconstructed salinity fields achieve resolutions smaller than 25 km. The evaluation of the method was conducted by comparing the results with *in-situ* data from thermosalinograph (TSG) measurements of the Oleander project. It revealed that reconstructed fields present more realistic small-scale variability than satellite SSS observations near the Gulf Stream. However, the method also showed an underestimation of frontal structures and their intensity on the continental shelf break. In the Sargasso Sea, reconstructed fields showed unrealistic salinity fronts inherited from the high variability observed in satellite SSS observations.

1.5 Objective of this thesis

The resolution of satellite SSS observations of the BMC does not allow the detection of fine structure and temporal evolution of cross-shelf exchanges (Guerrero et al., 2014; Manta et al.,

2022). Despite it, geostrophic currents derived from altimetry are a reliable indicator of the dynamics of the region and a valuable tool for tracking cross-shore water export (Manta et al., 2022; Strub et al., 2015).

The high mesoscale activity together with the small-scale salinity variability of the BMC makes it a suitable region to apply passive advection methods in order to reconstruct small-scale salinity structures. Using satellite SSS observations and geostrophic currents derived from altimetry, the objective of this work is to apply the Lagrangian reconstruction method developed by Barceló-Llull et al. (2021) for the validation of the method at the BMC region. First, an evaluation of large-scale signals of SSS is done using data from satellite SSS observations and *in-situ* based SSS fields. Then, the Lagrangian reconstruction technique is applied to satellite SSS observations to obtain the SSS reconstructed fields which are finally compared to *in-situ* observations from ship-based measurements.

2

Data

2.1 Satellite Observations

2.1.1 SMOS Sea Surface Salinity

Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) SSS maps are obtained from LOCEAN/ACRI-ST Expertise Center. They consist on de-biased gridded products of the Level 3 SMOS SSS 9-days running mean in its 9th version with a spatial resolution of 25×25 km. The maps are provided every 4 days covering the period from 2010 to 2023 and are freely available (<https://www.seanoe.org/data/00417/52804/>).

2.1.2 SMAP Sea Surface Salinity

Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) SSS global L3 products are developed by Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) offering daily maps based on SSS averages spanning an 8-day moving time window. The 5th version of the product is gridded at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ with a effective spatial resolution of ~ 60 km and it covers the period between 30 April 2015 - present. The dataset is freely available (https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/SMAP_JPL_L3_SSS_CAP_8DAY-RUNNINGMEAN_V5).

2.1.3 Geostrophic Currents Derived From Altimetry

The geostrophic currents are derived from altimeter satellite gridded sea level anomalies, which are computed with respect to a 1993-2012 mean. The L4 field is constructed by different altimeter missions datasets with a spatial resolution of 0.25° and a daily temporal resolution. This product is available at https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/viewer/expert?view=dataset&dataset=SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_L4_MY_008_047.

2.2 *In-situ* Data

2.2.1 ISAS20 ARGO Sea Surface Salinity

Argo is an international programme for ocean research that provides *in-situ* data of a 4000 profiling floats network. It has unrestricted access to global real-time observations of temperature, salinity and currents down to 2000m properly validated. The In Situ Analysis System (ISAS) produces three dimensional gridded fields of temperature and salinity based on observations of the Argo network using an optimal interpolation technique. ISAS20 ARGO uses the 8th version of ISAS to produce monthly climatologies with 187 vertical levels down to 500m depth and a horizontal

grid resolution of 0.5° . ISAS20 ARGO datasets are freely available at <https://www.seanoe.org/data/00412/52367/>.

2.2.2 Thermosalinograph data

The BMC region is strongly undersampled by the *in-situ* network of the Global Ocean Observing System (*OceanOPS Report Card 2023*, 2023) making the work of finding validation datasets challenging. The *in-situ* observations used for validation come from thermosalinograph (TSG) measurements of ship transects along the region. The two databases considered are illustrated on figure 2.1.

The first data comes from an oceanographic campaign conducted along the Uruguayan Economic Exclusive Zone aboard the Spanish Sarmiento de Gamboa Research Vessel between 9 April and 10 May 2016. It consisted on a sinuous trajectory within a small region near the coast divided in 12 along-shelf transects with an in-between distance of 25 km covering 320 km along-slope and 370 km across-slope. SSS measures were taken with a 1-min interval sampling using a Sea-Bird SEACAT SBE 21 TSG, together with SST and fluorescence. This dataset has been used by Manta et al. (2022) and it is freely available (<https://www.seanoe.org/data/00750/86206/>).

With the aim of analysing off-shore data one transect along the PS aboard the METEOR - IMO8411279 Research Vessel was selected from the Coriolis database (<https://www.coriolis.eu.org/Data-Products/Data-selection>) covering the first 10 days of 2022.

Figure 2.1: Transects of the TSG and the corresponding SSS measurements. The border colour of the transects indicates the database they come from.

3

Methods

3.1 Lagrangian reconstruction technique

3.1.1 Calculation of geostrophic velocities from altimetry

Geostrophic velocities are calculated from satellite altimetry data using sea surface height (SSH) gradients. Zonal and meridional geostrophic velocity components (u and v respectively) can be derived using the following formulas, which are based on the geostrophic balance:

$$u = -\frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \quad (3.1)$$

$$v = \frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \quad (3.2)$$

Where g is the acceleration due to gravity and f is the Coriolis parameter given by $f = 2\Omega \sin(\phi)$ being Ω the Earth's rotation rate and ϕ the latitude. h is the SSH and $\frac{\partial h}{\partial y}$ and $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$ denote the meridional and zonal gradients of SSH, respectively.

3.1.2 Parcels simulator

The transport of ocean properties can be considered from two different approaches. The Eulerian framework is based on the conservation of energy, mass and momentum in finite-volume cells forming a discrete grid and the water fluxes between them, while the Lagrangian approach traces particles along a trajectory through passive advection by ocean currents. Lagrangian simulations require an Eulerian field input for the hydrodynamical forcing to resolve the movement equations for each particle, while Eulerian simulations perform implicit arithmetic calculations needed of fast hardware processor and software parallelisation. The computational cost of Lagrangian simulations relies on access to the Eulerian fields to force the simulation (Kehl et al., 2021) which require a high-speed storage hardware interface.

Over the last two decades Lagrangian ocean analysis has become important in physical oceanography (van Sebille et al., 2018) and several open-source codes of Lagrangian simulators have been created by the community (Blanke and Raynaud, 1997; Döös et al., 2017; Paris et al., 2013). However, the volume of data storage required by these types of simulations demands more advanced optimisation strategies (Lange and van Sebille, 2017). Parcels ("Probably A Really Computationally Efficient Lagrangian Simulator") addresses these needs by developing an scalable and efficient Lagrangian simulator designed for handling with hydrodynamic data.

From a Lagrangian framework, the position of the particle \mathbf{X} is computed with the following equation:

$$\mathbf{X}(t + \Delta t) = \mathbf{X}(t) + \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, \tau) d\tau + \Delta \mathbf{X}_b(t) \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the velocity field at that position and $\Delta \mathbf{X}_b(t)$ the change in position because of buoyancy processes. Parcels uses a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme by default to integrate this equation and works with sets of particles whose state is defined by computational kernels highly customisable by the user to embrace more complex displacement schemes like turbulence or brownian motion.

The SSS reconstruction is based on the Lagrangian advection of passive tracers done with Parcels. It uses currents derived from altimetry as the velocity components (without considering diffusion terms) and the integration is done with a time-step of three hours. The simulation is executed with the JIT mode (just-in-time mode, see Lange and van Sebille, 2017) and has a recovery kernel for deleting particles out of the spatial domain of the simulation. The API can be found here <https://docs.oceanparcels.org/en/latest/reference.html>.

3.1.3 Reconstruction method

Small-scale SSS maps are built with the Lagrangian reconstruction method used in Barceló-Llull et al. (2021), which consists on the advection of passive salinity particles by geostrophic currents. The resulting product is a regular grid with 0.04° of resolution at the final time of the simulation t_f with salinity particles advected from the initial time $t_f - n$, where n is the number of days the particles are advected. The advection is done following a backward approach so the regular spacing of the grid is preserved in the final product. The method is implemented as follows:

1. A regular grid of particles with a resolution of 0.04° is advected backwards n days by the geostrophic currents derived from altimetry, from t_f to $t_f - n$.
2. The satellite SSS observations corresponding to day $t_f - n$ are interpolated onto the particle positions on the day $t_f - n$. With this, each particle is tagged with a value of salinity coming from satellite observations.
3. The salinity particles return to the regular grid configuration at t_f . The reconstructed salinity map is a plot of the salinity values of the particles at their final positions.

Satellite SSS observations have lower temporal resolution than geostrophic currents so the election of n is determined by the availability of the satellite SSS observations. Even that these products provide SSS maps for concrete days, they are the mean values of the observations from several days. Despite that, for the comparative analysis between the satellite SSS observations and the reconstructed fields, the resolution of the reconstructed fields is the same as the satellite SSS observations. With this, n is restricted to a multiple of the temporal resolution of the satellite SSS observations, so there are always satellite SSS observations available at $t_f - n$ for the reconstruction, and at t_f to compare the reconstructed fields with.

3.2 Reconstruction validation with *in-situ* data

The validation of the reconstruction method is performed by comparing the reconstructed SSS fields with *in-situ* SSS observations from TSG. The reconstructed fields are interpolated at the spatial coordinates of the TSG observation. The temporal resolution of the TSG is higher than the reconstructed maps (they have the same resolution as satellite SSS observations) so the TSG observations are compared with the nearest in time interpolated value. The satellite SSS observations are interpolated to compare them with the TSG observations.

The comparison between the interpolated data and the TSG observations is done through a Taylor diagram. Taylor diagrams are graphical summaries of the statistical similarities of one or more fields with a reference observation. The similarities are quantified in terms of the correlation coefficient, the root-mean-square difference (RMSD) and the standard deviation (SD).

4

Results

4.1 Evaluating large-scale signals

For the application of the Lagrangian reconstruction method, it is fundamental to choose a satellite SSS dataset that accurately represents the main features of the region. Nowadays, there are two satellite missions measuring SSS: SMOS and SMAP. Observations from both missions are compared to the Argo-based SSS climatology, which serves as the best representation of the large-scale distribution in the region of study.

The temporal mean SSS of the period 2016-2022 derived from Argo, SMOS and SMAP are shown in figure 4.1. Both satellite mean products (SMOS and SMAP) agree well with *in-situ* data (ISAS). Satellite observations capture the major rivers' discharge (for e.g. the Mississippi, Amazon, Congo, and La Plata rivers in the Atlantic) and reproduce relatively well the high salinity tropical regions (consistent with the evaporation minus precipitation budget). Note that satellite-derived SSS products present some unphysical anomalies such as the sparkly structures of the SMOS SSS located at 15°S 170°W and 20°S 55°E, south of Madagascar Island. Significant difference between satellite and *in-situ* SSS can be observed in polar regions, which can be attributed to the limited number of observations in these regions and the quality of satellite-derived SSS due to the presence of sea-ice.

Focusing on the study region, figure 4.2 shows the climatologies of both satellite products centered in the SA region. It also shows the differences of both products with the Argo-based climatology, calculated with the interpolation of the ISAS SSS field at the SMOS and SMAP spatial coordinates. Along the coast, satellite SSS is generally fresher than in the ISAS dataset. Over the open ocean, the difference in the mean SSS is small (<0.5 psu) with no large-scale errors. Over the southwest Atlantic, the SMOS product seems to agree better with observations than the SMAP product. This is particularly visible over the PS, the MC, and the southern BC. For this reason the SMOS SSS product is used for the reconstruction over the BMC.

4.2 Comparing the reconstructed fields with *in-situ* data

The Lagrangian reconstruction method has been applied at each period covered by the TSG data (9 April-10 May 2016 and 1-10 January 2022) resulting in a reconstructed field every 4 days. The ocean currents in the BMC are particularly intense and experiments using $n > 8$ show unrealistic patterns. For this reason, the particles advection days (see section 3.1.3) considered are $n = 4$ and $n = 8$. Figure 4.3 shows the original SMOS SSS field, the geostrophic currents and the result of the Lagrangian SSS reconstruction for 26 April 2016 using $n = 4$. The white-bordered

Figure 4.1: SSS Climatology from the Argo-based product (top), SMOS (middle panel) and SMAP (bottom panel). The climatology corresponds to the mean value of SSS of the period of 2016-2020. The study region is highlighted with a black box.

Figure 4.2: SSS climatology in the South Atlantic Ocean for both satellite observation products (left SMOS, right SMAP). Bottom images correspond to the difference of each satellite product with the Argo-based climatology.

data corresponds to the TSG observations from that period.

Over the shelf, low salinity waters from the RdIP discharge spread northwards, while off the shelf the confluence of salty waters from the BC and fresher waters from the MC create some eddy-like structures and SSS fronts. Geostrophic currents show the flow of the MC and the BC currents and its retroflexion at the confluence region. They also reveal the presence of several eddies in this region, two anticyclonic eddies are located at $38^{\circ}\text{S } 52^{\circ}\text{W}$ and $41^{\circ}\text{S } 52^{\circ}\text{W}$ surrounded by several cyclonic eddies. Over the shelf, the currents capture the northward flowing of the RdIP waters and an off-shelf flow at $36^{\circ}\text{S } 52.5^{\circ}\text{W}$, crossing the TSG measurements. The reconstructed SSS field presents finer resolution compared to the original SMOS SSS field. It captures the eddy activity of the confluence region showed by the geostrophic currents and unravels a clear cross-shelf exchange plume of freshwater at the northern side of RdIP, going eastwards. This off-shelf plume agrees with the structure observed by the TSG and is not detected by the original SMOS SSS.

The TSG signal (bottom panel on figure 4.3) indicates a salinity front that abruptly drops from 36 to 32.5 psu at $\sim 07:20$ hours and rises again at $\sim 19:00$. The SMOS original data has SSS values around 36 psu at the start of the transect, similar to TSG values, but these values

decrease to 34 psu at $\sim 8:00$ and remain similar thereafter. In contrast, the reconstructed SSS fields capture very well the frontal structure observed by the TSG. At the start of the transect, the field reconstructed with $n = 4$ shows salinity values around 36 psu which drop to ~ 32.5 psu from approximately 8:00 to 18:30, before rising abruptly to 36 psu.

Figure 4.3: SMOS SSS (top left), geostrophic velocities derived from altimetry superimposed on SMOS SSS (top middle), and reconstructed SSS field (top right) for the 26 of April of 2016. The TSG data corresponding to the period 24-28 April 2016 is superposed with a white border to the three maps at the top of the figure. The bottom panel compares the TSG data with the interpolated values of the SMOS SSS and the reconstructed field.

Figure 4.4 presents four different examples of TSG transects. These transects have been selected based on the variability of SSS along the transect (in particular the presence of SSS fronts) and the good performance of the reconstruction method. In all cases, the reconstructed fields (using $n = 4$) improve the original observations of SMOS SSS when compared to the TSG data. The statistical similarities of the different interpolated fields with the TSG observations are illustrated on a Taylor diagram.

The first transect corresponds to the one shown on figure 4.3. Its Taylor diagram indicates that the 4-days reconstruction field maintains the correlation of the SMOS SSS but its SD is closer to the one of the TSG, resulting in a lower RMSD (orange lines). The field reconstructed with $n = 8$ overestimates the intensity of the front, which shows values as low as 30 psu. Using $n = 8$ days, the advection of fresh shelf water seems to be too strong compared to the TSG observation, resulting in a smaller correlation coefficient and stronger SD (stronger fronts).

The TSG observations shown on the second example indicate a SSS front at the start of the transect, starting with salinity values around 27 psu and reaching up to 36 psu at about 03:00. This sharp increase in salinity is not captured by the SMOS SSS, which starts with higher values (~ 28 psu) and rises up to 33 psu at $\sim 03:30$ with a smoother trend than the one captured by the TSG. Despite that, at the end of the transect the SMOS SSS reaches 36 psu, similar to

Figure 4.4: Four different SSS transects measured by the TSG compared with the interpolated values of SMOS SSS and the reconstructed fields. Temporal evolution (left) and the corresponding Taylor diagram (right). The root-mean standard difference is represented by the orange lines.

the observed by the TSG. The reconstructed SSS fields reflect the sharpness of the initial front and maintain similar values with the TSG along the transect. The reconstruction for $n = 4$ overestimates the salinity value at the start of the transect and shows values similar to the SMOS SSS but captures the frontal rise precisely. On the contrary, the reconstruction with $n = 8$ starts with salinity values around 27 like the TSG, but the increment of salinity does not occur at the same location as the TSG observation. Statistically, both reconstructed fields have higher correlation coefficient and RMSD with the TSG observation, especially the 8-days reconstructed field, which reduces the RMSD by 0.5 psu respect to the SMOS SSS.

The third case shows three sharp increments of salinity captured by the TSG which go from 33.5 psu to 36.5 psu, one from 02:45 to 16:00, the second one from 08:30 to 13:00 and the last one from 15:30 to 17:00. The SMOS SSS detects values between 34.5 and 35.5 psu with three relative maxima located at similar positions than the maxima observed by the TSG. In this example, the reconstructed fields present different behaviours. The reconstruction with $n = 4$ starts with a higher value of salinity than the TSG observation (34.5 psu) and captures the structure of the three TSG maxima with lower values of salinity (up to 35 psu). The $n = 8$ reconstruction, while starting with a value similar to the TSG, diverges significantly from the observed values afterward. Note that both reconstructed SSS fields create a frontal structure between 05:00 and 08:15 which is not observed by the TSG or the SMOS SSS. The diagram shows weak correlation ($R \sim 0$) between the 8-days advection reconstruction and the TSG observations. Using $n = 4$ days, the correlation coefficient reaches 0.7 and weaker SD values compared to the TSG data.

The last transect shows a low-salinity frontal structure observed by the TSG starting with salinity values ~ 35.25 psu, decreasing to 33.5 psu at 12:45, and rising again to values around 36 psu at 14:00 the following day. This transect covers a larger time scale (it lasts a day and a half) compared to the previous three, which lasted a few hours. The SMOS SSS does capture the low frequency variability of the SSS ($R = 0.7$) but does not capture the sharpness of the front (high RMSD). At the start of the transect, the SMOS SSS values are similar to the ones captured by the TSG, but at around 07:30 the values of salinity detected by the SMOS SSS start to decrease smoothly until they reach 33.75 psu. These values are maintained until 01:20 where they go up to 35.25 at 14:00. The reconstructed fields align more closely with the TSG than the SMOS SSS ($R = 0.85$). Both fields capture the sharp decrease of salinity at 12:45 and a clear improvement of the SSS front at 14:00. Both reconstructions ($n = 4$ and $n = 8days$) therefore improve the RMSD with value of 0.4 psu.

Discussion and conclusions

The comparison of different SSS observations products done in section 4.1 reveals how these products resolve the large-scale SSS and which of these products is the most accurate representation of the SSS distribution of the BMC region. One of the main drivers of cross-shelf exchanges of the region is the BC and MC interaction with the adjacent shelf. In particular, an accurate representation of the confluence of the two currents is essential to characterize the SSS fronts generated by the export of low salinity shelf waters. The SMOS SSS represents the principal large-scale features detected on the Argo-derived climatology with higher accuracy than the SMAP SSS, especially in the southern portion of the SA Ocean. In addition, the ISAS climatology underestimates the freshwater content in rivers' discharge regions compared to the satellite SSS observations, probably due to the limited number of observations in these regions. From the three SSS products available, the SMOS SSS is the more suitable large-scale representation of the BMC region.

The validation of the SSS reconstruction method presented on section 4.2 demonstrates an improvement in the representation of mesoscale features in the reconstructed fields compared to the original SMOS SSS observations. We find that the reconstruction method is able to reproduce some of the cross-shelf exchanges at the BMC that are captured by TSG observations. The comparison of the SMOS SSS with the $n = 4$ and $n = 8$ SSS reconstructed fields with TSG data shows that SMOS SSS product has less variability than the TSG observations and also captures smoother structures. Most of the sharp changes in salinity captured by the TSG are not well-represented by the SMOS SSS. In contrast, SSS reconstructed fields show better agreement with the TSG observations on intense salinity fronts, though the variability of the smaller scales is also not well-represented by the SSS reconstructed fields.

Even though all the validation examples indicate a better performance of the reconstructed fields compared to the SMOS SSS observations, not all the reconstructed transects in this work exhibit the same result. Approximately half of the reconstructed SSS fields used for validation were unable to represent the variability observed by the TSG and did not improve the results of the SMOS SSS. Satellite altimetry products have low resolution and are unable to capture small eddies, often misinterpreting the signal associated with them (Amores et al., 2018). These inaccurate altimetry observations result in false mesoscale structure in the reconstructed SSS fields. Additionally, satellite SSS products have low effective resolution on coastal areas, which increases the inaccuracy of the SSS reconstruction at the BMC.

We showed that the Lagrangian reconstruction method captures mesoscale structures detected by *in-situ* observations at the BMC region and improves the effective resolution of SSS satellite observations. However, the good performance of the method does not apply to all the situa-

tions considered in this study. Geostrophic motion is an approximation of the surface current. Ageostrophic motions that arise from processes like mixing, Ekman transport or upwelling mechanisms on coastal regions contribute to small-scale salinity variability but are not considered in this work. In addition, the SA Ocean is a strongly undersampled region, particularly the *in-situ* measurements available at the BMC are scarce and very separated in time. Because of that, the validation of the reconstructed SSS fields has been limited.

Future work would first start by finding new *in-situ* data for validation in order to offer a larger perspective of the capacity of the reconstruction. Additionally, the dataset of satellite SSS observations used for the reconstruction could be improved by considering the SMOS/SMAP merged product available in the Copernicus Marine Service webpage (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MULTIOBS_GLO_PHY_SSS_L4_MY_015_015/description). Finally, a new product of reconstructed SSS field covering the period 2010-present could be created. This product would help in the understanding of water masses associated with mesoscale features and could be compared with the SSS from ocean models.

Code availability

The scripts and data used for the reconstruction and validation for the 9 April-10 May 2016 period are available at the GitHub repository <https://github.com/cmartisolana/TFM.git>. All codes are written in Python and integrated in Jupyter notebooks with detailed explanations.

Bibliography

- Amores, A., Jordà, G., Arsouze, T., & Le Sommer, J. (2018). Up to What Extent Can We Characterize Ocean Eddies Using Present-Day Gridded Altimetric Products? *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *123*(10), 7220–7236. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JC014140>
- Banks, C. J., Srokosz, M. A., Cipollini, P., Snaith, H. M., Blundell, J. R., Gommenginger, C. P., & Tzortzi, E. (2016). Reduced ascending/descending pass bias in SMOS salinity data demonstrated by observing westward-propagating features in the South Indian Ocean. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, *180*, 154–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2016.02.035>
- Barceló-Llull, B., Drushka, K., & Gaube, P. (2021). Lagrangian Reconstruction to Extract Small-Scale Salinity Variability From SMAP Observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *126*(3), e2020JC016477. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016477>
- Blanke, B., & Raynaud, S. (1997). Kinematics of the Pacific Equatorial Undercurrent: An Eulerian and Lagrangian Approach from GCM Results. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *27*(6), 1038–1053. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1997\)027<1038:KOTPEU>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1997)027<1038:KOTPEU>2.0.CO;2)
- Calado, L., da Silveira, I. C. A., Gangopadhyay, A., & de Castro, B. M. (2010). Eddy-induced upwelling off Cape São Tomé (22°S, Brazil). *Continental Shelf Research*, *30*(10), 1181–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2010.03.007>
- Chelton, D. B., Schlax, M. G., & Samelson, R. M. (2011). Global observations of nonlinear mesoscale eddies. *Progress in Oceanography*, *91*(2), 167–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2011.01.002>
- Combes, V., & Matano, R. P. (2014). A two-way nested simulation of the oceanic circulation in the Southwestern Atlantic. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *119*(2), 731–756. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC009498>
- Combes, V., & Matano, R. P. (2018). The Patagonian shelf circulation: Drivers and variability. *Progress in Oceanography*, *167*, 24–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2018.07.003>
- Combes, V., Matano, R. P., & Palma, E. D. (2021). Circulation and Cross-Shelf Exchanges in the Northern Shelf Region of the Southwestern Atlantic: Kinematics. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *126*(4), e2020JC016959. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016959>
- Combes, V., Matano, R. P., & Palma, E. D. (2023). Circulation and Cross-Shelf Exchanges in the Northern Shelf of the Southwestern Atlantic: Dynamics. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *128*(7), e2023JC019887. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JC019887>
- Dencausse, G., Morrow, R., Rogé, M., & Fleury, S. (2014). Lateral stirring of large-scale tracer fields by altimetry. *Ocean Dynamics*, *64*(1), 61–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-013-0671-8>
- Desprès, A., Reverdin, G., & d’Ovidio, F. (2011). Mechanisms and spatial variability of meso scale frontogenesis in the northwestern subpolar gyre. *Ocean Modelling*, *39*(1), 97–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2010.12.005>

- Döös, K., Jönsson, B., & Kjellsson, J. (2017). Evaluation of oceanic and atmospheric trajectory schemes in the TRACMASS trajectory model v6.0. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10(4), 1733–1749. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-1733-2017>
- Foltz, G. R., Grodsky, S. A., Carton, J. A., & McPhaden, M. J. (2004). Seasonal salt budget of the northwestern tropical Atlantic Ocean along 38°W. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 109(C3). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2003JC002111>
- Grodsky, S. A., Reul, N., Chapron, B., Carton, J. A., & Bryan, F. O. (2017). Interannual surface salinity on Northwest Atlantic shelf. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122(5), 3638–3659. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JC012580>
- Guerrero, R. A., Piola, A. R., Fenco, H., Matano, R. P., Combes, V., Chao, Y., James, C., Palma, E. D., Saraceno, M., & Strub, P. T. (2014). The salinity signature of the cross-shelf exchanges in the Southwestern Atlantic Ocean: Satellite observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 119(11), 7794–7810. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JC010113>
- Guinder, V., Ferronato, C., Dogliotti, A., Segura, V., & Lutz, V. (2024). The phytoplankton of the Patagonian Shelf-Break Front. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.169029006.64453530/v2>
- Häkkinen, S. (2002). Surface salinity variability in the northern North Atlantic during recent decades. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 107(C12), SRF 4–1–SRF 4–12. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JC000812>
- Hasson, A., Puy, M., Boutin, J., Guilyardi, E., & Morrow, R. (2018). Northward Pathway Across the Tropical North Pacific Ocean Revealed by Surface Salinity: How do El Niño Anomalies Reach Hawaii? *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 123(4), 2697–2715. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC013423>
- Kehl, C., van Sebille, E., & Gibson, A. (2021, April). Speeding up Python-based Lagrangian Fluid-Flow Particle Simulations via Dynamic Collection Data Structures. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2105.00057>
- Lange, M., & van Sebille, E. (2017). Parcels v0.9: Prototyping a Lagrangian ocean analysis framework for the petascale age. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10(11), 4175–4186. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-4175-2017>
- Lehahn, Y., d’Ovidio, F., & Koren, I. (2018). A Satellite-Based Lagrangian View on Phytoplankton Dynamics. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 10(Volume 10, 2018), 99–119. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-121916-063204>
- Manta, G., Speich, S., Barreiro, M., Trinchin, R., de Mello, C., Laxenaire, R., & Piola, A. R. (2022). Shelf Water Export at the Brazil-Malvinas Confluence Evidenced From Combined in situ and Satellite Observations. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.857594>
- Matano, R. P., Combes, V., Piola, A. R., Guerrero, R., Palma, E. D., Ted Strub, P., James, C., Fenco, H., Chao, Y., & Saraceno, M. (2014). The salinity signature of the cross-shelf exchanges in the Southwestern Atlantic Ocean: Numerical simulations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 119(11), 7949–7968. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JC010116>
- OceanOPS Report Card 2023* (tech. rep.). (2023). Retrieved August 17, 2024, from <https://www.ocean-ops.org/reportcard2023/>
- Palma, E., & Matano, R. (2018). South Atlantic Circulation and Variability from a Data Assimilating Model. *Marine Pollution and Climate Change*.
- Palma, E. D., Matano, R. P., Piola, A. R., & Sitz, L. E. (2004). A comparison of the circulation patterns over the Southwestern Atlantic Shelf driven by different wind stress climatologies. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 31(24). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004GL021068>
- Paris, C. B., Helgers, J., van Sebille, E., & Srinivasan, A. (2013). Connectivity Modeling System: A probabilistic modeling tool for the multi-scale tracking of biotic and abiotic variability in the ocean. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 42, 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2012.12.006>

- Pietri, A., Testor, P., Echevin, V., Chaigneau, A., Mortier, L., Eldin, G., & Grados, C. (2013). Finescale Vertical Structure of the Upwelling System off Southern Peru as Observed from Glider Data. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *43*(3), 631–646. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-12-035.1>
- Piola, A. R., Campos, E. J. D., Möller Jr., O. O., Charo, M., & Martinez, C. (2000). Subtropical Shelf Front off eastern South America. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *105*(C3), 6565–6578. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JC000300>
- Piola, A. R., & Matano, R. (2001, December). Brazil And Falklands (malvinas) Currents [Journal Abbreviation: Encyclopedia of Ocean Sciences]. In *Encyclopedia of Ocean Sciences* (pp. 340–349, Vol. 1). <https://doi.org/10.1006/rwos.2001.0358>
- Piola, A. R., Möller, O. O., Guerrero, R. A., & Campos, E. J. D. (2008). Variability of the subtropical shelf front off eastern South America: Winter 2003 and summer 2004. *Continental Shelf Research*, *28*(13), 1639–1648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2008.03.013>
- Rhein, M., Rintoul, S., Aoki, S., Campos, E., Chambers, D., Feely, R., Gulev, S., Johnson, G., Josey, S., Kostianoy, A., Mauritzen, C., Roemmich, D., Talley, L., & Wang, F. (2013). Observations: Ocean. In *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/WG1AR5_Chapter03_FINAL.pdf
- Rogé, M., Morrow, R. A., & Dencausse, G. (2015). Altimetric Lagrangian advection to reconstruct Pacific Ocean fine-scale surface tracer fields. *Ocean Dynamics*, *65*(9), 1249–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-015-0872-4>
- Steele, M., Ermold, W., & Zhang, J. (2008). Arctic Ocean surface warming trends over the past 100 years. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *35*(2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007GL031651>
- Strub, P. T., James, C., Combes, V., Matano, R. P., Piola, A. R., Palma, E. D., Saraceno, M., Guerrero, R. A., Fenco, H., & Ruiz-Etcheverry, L. A. (2015). Altimeter-derived seasonal circulation on the southwest Atlantic shelf: 27°–43°S. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *120*(5), 3391–3418. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JC010769>
- van Sebille, E., Griffies, S. M., Abernathy, R., Adams, T. P., Berloff, P., Biastoch, A., Blanke, B., Chassignet, E. P., Cheng, Y., Cotter, C. J., Deleersnijder, E., Döös, K., Drake, H. F., Drijfhout, S., Gary, S. F., Heemink, A. W., Kjellsson, J., Koszalka, I. M., Lange, M., ... Zika, J. D. (2018). Lagrangian ocean analysis: Fundamentals and practices. *Ocean Modelling*, *121*, 49–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2017.11.008>
- Vinogradova, N. T., & Ponte, R. M. (2017). In Search of Fingerprints of the Recent Intensification of the Ocean Water Cycle. *Journal of Climate*, *30*(14), 5513–5528. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0626.1>
- Yin, X., Boutin, J., Reverdin, G., Lee, T., Arnault, S., & Martin, N. (2014). SMOS Sea Surface Salinity signals of tropical instability waves [Publisher: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd]. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *119*(11), 7811–7826. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JC009960>